

Catalytic and Kinetic Behaviour of Yeast Glucose-6-phosphate Dehydrogenase in Reverse Micellar Solution of Mixed Surfactants in Non-aqueous Solvents

TAPAS K. DE and S. S. KATIYAR*

Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology, Kanpur-208 016

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The activity and kinetic properties of glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase (D-glucose-6-phosphate: NADP⁺ oxidoreductase, EC 1.1.1.49, G-6-PDH) have been investigated in reverse micelles formed by mixture of two surfactants, namely, sodium bis(2-ethylhexyl)sulphosuccinate (AOT) and polyoxyethylene(5)octylphenol (Triton X-45) (1 : 1 molar ratio) in n-heptane. The pH profile is significantly altered in reverse micelles with respect to water. However, the pH for optimum activity in reverse micelles is almost same as in aqueous buffer. The activity of the enzyme is markedly affected by the micellar conditions, in particular by the water content w_o ($w_o = [\text{H}_2\text{O}]/[\text{Surfactant}]$) and surfactant concentration. The activity versus degree of hydration (w_o) of the surfactant profile exhibits bell-shaped curves centred on two optimal degrees of hydration. The enzyme follows Michaelis-Menten kinetics within a specified concentration range. The K_m values for the substrate, glucose-6-phosphate and coenzyme (NADP⁺) were determined at $w_o = 27.8$ and pH = 9.7. The K_m values were higher in reverse micellar solution compared to the values in aqueous buffer. The enzyme was found to be superactive at the optimum conditions of pH 9.7, water pool size 27.8 and total surfactant concentration 0.2 M. Activity and general behaviour of the enzyme in the water pool in the reverse micelles have been explained on the basis of unique properties of water in the microcaptive environment in reverse micellar solution.

The use of enzymes as biocatalysts in non-aqueous media have received increasing attention. However, replacement of water as a reaction medium by an organic solvent is usually accompanied by either a total denaturation of the enzyme or drastic decrease of its catalytic activity. To perform biocatalytic processes in non-aqueous solvents a molecule of the enzyme can be protected from unfavourable action of an organic solvent by means of surfactants in the form of reverse micelles¹. The retention of catalytic activity is due to the entrapment of enzyme molecules into aqueous microdroplets, the enzyme being protected against denaturing contact with the outer organic phase by a water-rich layer^{2,3}.

Most of the enzymes studied so far in the reverse micelles are of low molecular weight and of one or two sub-units. Our interest was to study the activity of a relatively big enzyme with more sub-units. In the present paper we report the solubilisation of glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase (G-6-PDH) in the reverse micellar solution of sodium bis(2-ethylhexyl)sulphosuccinate (AOT) and polyoxyethylene(5)octylphenol (Triton X-45) (1 : 1 molar ratio) in n-heptane. Glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase from yeast is a relatively big enzyme

with molecular weight ~212000 having four sub-units⁴. A detailed and systematic study on the activity, stability and kinetic characteristics of yeast glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase in the reverse micelles of mixed surfactant has been reported. The enzyme catalysed the reaction,

Results and Discussion

Effect of degree of hydration (w_o) on enzyme activity : The plot of percent control activity of glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase as a function of degree of hydration at different pH is shown in Fig. 1. Here pH refers to pH of the stock buffer solution. At all pH values, the plot was found to be bell-shaped curve having two maxima. As the water pool size increases the activity of the enzyme also increases and after showing two maxima, the activity at higher w_o flattens out or decreases. At pH 9.4–9.7 where the reverse micellar solution solubilises maximum amount of water, the enzyme shows higher activity. For example, maximum activity was 164% of control at $w_o = 27.8$, pH = 9.7.

The plot of activity versus w_0 has been found to be bell-shaped for many enzymes, viz. α -chymotrypsin⁸, alkaline phosphatase⁹, lipase¹⁰, lysozyme¹¹, glutathione reductase¹², lactate dehydrogenase¹³, malate dehydrogenase⁷, etc. The bell-shaped dependence of enzyme activity upon w_0 represents a general feature of the enzyme behaviour in micellar solution. In the present case

Fig. 1. Activity of G-6-PDH in mixed micelles of AOT-Triton X-45 n-heptane versus degree of hydration (w_0). The activity is expressed relative to the activity in aqueous buffer. The concentrations were [AOT] = 0.1M, [Triton X-45] = 0.1M, [NADP⁺] = 0.11 mM, [G-6-P] = 0.35 mM. Buffer was 100 mM glycine-KOH, [G-6-PDH] = 0.1 μ g ml⁻¹.

too we get bell-shaped curve which is centred on two optimal degrees of hydration. This is an unusual observation. So far there are only two reports, swine muscle lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) in ACT/octane¹⁴ and γ -glutamyl-transferase¹⁵, where bell-shaped curves centred on several optimal degrees of hydration were observed. These optima are attributed to the entrapment of dimers, tetramers and octamers (i.e. 2-tetramers) of LDH in the reverse micelles as a function of micelle size which in turn is a function of degree of hydration. The same interpretation seems to be valid in the case of yeast glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase which is an oligomeric enzyme of four sub-units in the presence of NADP⁺.

Effect of pH on enzyme activity : The rate of an enzymatic reaction and its characteristic kinetic parameters depend on the pH of the buffer solution. When an enzyme is transferred from aqueous buffer solution to the water pool of the reverse micellar solution, the obvious expectation is that the reaction

will depend on the pH of the water pool. The variation of activity of G-6-PDH with change of pH (pH of the stock buffer solution) at fixed values of w_0 is shown in Fig. 2. The plots at different water pools are bell-shaped. At all the water pools the maximum activity is observed at pH 9.7. In the pH

Fig. 2. The percentage of control activity profile of G-6-PDH in AOT-Triton X-45 n-heptane reverse micelle as a function of pH at different water pools. The concentrations were [AOT] = 0.1M, [Triton X-45] = 0.1M, [NADP⁺] = 0.11 mM, [G-6-P] = 0.35 mM. Buffer was 100 mM glycine-KOH, pH = 9.4, [G-6-PDH] = 0.1 μ g ml⁻¹.

range 9.5–9.9, enzyme shows higher activity at different water pools. At pH below 9.0, the enzyme does not show any activity. The maximum activity was obtained at pH 9.7 and water pool 27.8. The pH for maximum activity is shifted slightly to higher value compared to aqueous buffer. In general, it is found that pH profile for enzymes in reverse micelles shifts to the alkaline side^{7,8,11}.

Small difference (~0.3 unit) in optimum pH in aqueous and reverse micelles in the case of G-6-PDH indicates that even in the micellar micro-environment at condition for maximum activity, pK_a of amino acid residues remain almost unchanged.

Effect of surfactant concentration of enzyme activity : Surfactant concentration is one of the critical parameters in the determination of the optimum conditions for enzyme reaction in reverse micellar solution. In the present study, we have used reverse micellar solution of mixed surfactant. The effect of surfactant concentration has been studied

in two different ways, viz. (i) changing the ratio of surfactant concentration, keeping water pool size (w_o) and total surfactant concentration (0.2 M) constant and (ii) varying the total surfactant concentration and keeping ratio of two surfactant concentrations and water pool size (w_o) invariant.

Fig. 3 shows enzyme activity as a function of the ratio of concentrations of AOT and Triton X-45 water pool sizes 27.8 and 38.9. The data demonstrate that the enzyme is most active when

Fig. 3. Dependence of G-6-PDH activity on ratio of $([AOT]/[Triton\ X-45])$ of surfactant concentration at $w_o = 27.8$, pH = 9.7 and $w_o = 38.9$, pH = 9.7 in AOT-Triton X-45 n-heptane reverse micellar system. The other concentrations were same as in Fig. 2.

concentrations of AOT and Triton X-45 are nearly equal. At this ratio the enzyme is highly active. On the other hand, at high concentration of ACT or at high concentration of Triton X-45 the enzyme shows poor activity.

When we change ratio of surfactant concentration it means that we are approaching to a reverse micellar solution of one single surfactant from other surfactant. In either of the surfactants the enzyme is less active and the combination of equal amounts of the surfactants provides the suitable environment for good activity.

Fig. 4 is the plot of percentage control activity against total surfactant concentration when ratio of two surfactant concentrations and water pool size are invariant. The result indicates that at lower concentration of total surfactant concentration the activity is less. With increase of total surfactant concentration activity increases and then attains a

saturation value. In the range of 0.11–0.18 M total surfactant concentration the activity of enzyme reaches its maximum value for the particular water

Fig. 4. Dependence of G-6-PDH activity on total surfactant concentrations in AOT-Triton X-45 n-heptane reverse micellar system at $w_o = 27.8$, pH = 9.7 $[AOT]/[Triton\ X-45] = 1$ and $w_o = 38.9$, pH = 9.7, $[AOT]/[Triton\ X-45] = 1$. Other concentrations were same as in Fig. 3.

pool size. It shows that equal amount of two surfactants is a critical ratio and is a necessary requirement for maximum activity of the enzyme. At low concentrations of total surfactant the enzyme molecules are not well-protected from the unfavourable action of organic solvent.

In reverse micellar solution study on the dependence of the enzyme reaction rate with substrate and coenzyme concentrations shows that the glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase follows Michaelis-Menten kinetics. Effect of NADP⁺ concentration and G-6-P concentration separately (keeping concentration of other component constant) are shown in Figs. 5 and 6. The initial velocity of the reaction initially increases linearly and then reaches a maximum. With further increase of NADP⁺ the reaction velocity remains at its saturation value. However in the case of G-6-P, the velocity reaches a maximum and then shows a decrease with increase of G-6-P concentration which is indicative of inhibition.

At high G-6-P concentration the deviation from Michaelis-Menten kinetics occurs because of substrate inhibition. Due to this substrate inhibition hyperbolic kinetics with an asymptote V_{max} may not apply¹⁶. When initial velocity of enzyme reaction is plotted against concentration of G-6-P, maximum velocity is obtained at 400 μM and at concentration beyond 400 μM G-6-P shows substrate inhibition. This phenomenon of substrate inhibition may be

due to formation of tight substrate-NADPH-enzyme abortive complex.

Fig. 5. Dependence of G-6-PDH activity on NADP^+ concentrations in 0.1M AOT and 0.1M Triton X-45 mixture in n-heptane at $\omega_0 = 27.8$ and $\text{pH} = 9.7$. The concentration of G-6-P was 0.35 mM and buffer was 100 mM glycine-KOH.

Fig. 6. Effect of G-6-P concentrations on G-6-PDH activity in 0.1M AOT and 0.1M Triton X-45 mixture in n-heptane at $\omega_0 = 27.8$ and $\text{pH} = 9.7$. The concentration of NADP^+ was 0.11 mM and buffer was 100 mM glycine-KOH.

Double reciprocal plots : Variation of inverse of G-6-PDH catalysed reaction rate with inverse of NADP^+ concentrations at four fixed concentrations of G-6-P is shown in Fig. 7. These plots are linear and meet on x-axis. Data for the primary plots of Figs. 7 and 8 were obtained by observing the effect

Fig. 7. Lineweaver-Burk plots for initial G-6-PDH rate with NADP^+ concentrations in 0.1M AOT and 0.1M Triton X-45 in n-heptane at different G-6-P concentrations at $\omega_0 = 27.8$ and $\text{pH} = 9.7$. Buffer was 100 mM glycine-KOH.

Fig. 8. Double reciprocal plots for initial G-6-PDH rate with G-6-P concentrations in 0.1M AOT and 0.1M Triton X-45 mixture in n-heptane at different NADP^+ concentrations and $\omega_0 = 27.8$ and $\text{pH} = 9.7$. Buffer was 100 mM glycine-KOH.

of substrate and coenzyme concentrations on G-6-PDH activity at $\omega_0 = 27.8$, $\text{pH} = 9.7$ in 0.1M AOT and 0.1M Triton X-100 (1 : 1) in n-heptane. The Michaelis constants (K_m) for NADP^+ and G-6-P were determined from the secondary plots obtained by plotting intercept of $1/V$ axis of one substrates against reciprocal of concentration of other substrate. The values are summarised in Table 1.

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISTIC CONSTANTS OF GLUCOSE-6-PHOSPHATE DEHYDROGENASE

Parameter*	0.1M AOT and 0.1M Triton X-45 mixture in n-heptane, $w_o = 27.8$ (pH = 9.7, 100 mM glycine-KOH)	Standard deviation	Tris buffer pH=8.0, 30°, 10 ⁻² M MgCl ₂
$(K_m^{NADP^+})_{ov}^M$	3.22×10^{-5}	0.226×10^{-5}	2.0×10^{-6}
$(K_m^{NADP^+})_{wp}^M$	3.22×10^{-4}		
$(K_m^{G-6-P})_{ov}^M$	6.896×10^{-5}	0.898×10^{-5}	2.0×10^{-5}
$(K_m^{G-6-P})_{wp}^M$	6.890×10^{-4}		
$(K_m^{NADP^+})_{ov}^M$	3.478×10^{-5}		
$(K_m^{NADP^+})_{wp}^M$	3.475×10^{-4}		
V_{max} , $\mu\text{mol dm}^{-3} \text{min}^{-1}$ (mg enzyme) ⁻¹	183.900		133.87 (100 mM glycine-KOH, pH = 9.4)

*ov = Overall; wp = water pool.

The comparison of data in Table 1 shows that in reverse micelles $(K_m)_{ov}$ for NADP⁺ increases 16.1 times and $(K_m)_{ov}$ for G-6-P increases 3.4 times in comparison to their values in aqueous medium. On the other hand, $(K_m)_{wp}$ of NADP⁺ is 161 times and $(K_m)_{wp}$ of G-6-P is 34.5 times of their values in aqueous medium. $(K_m)_{ov}$ in reverse micellar solution is taken as the valid one since reverse micellar solution behaves as a homogeneous solution and therefore substrate concentration and coenzyme concentration are considered for overall volume. The increase in $(K_m)_{ov}$ signifies that enzyme-substrate complex is significantly destabilised as compared to that in aqueous buffer.

Conclusion : A relatively big enzyme, glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase, with four subunits has been successfully solubilised in reverse micellar solution of mixed surfactant. Experimentally determined reaction rates for the enzyme from yeast show two optimal degrees of hydration in sharp contrast to that for the same enzyme from *Leuconostoc* microorganisms. Another interesting observation is that the enzyme activity depends not only on the substrate concentration and concentration of reverse micelle but also on the composition of the surfactants used to prepare reverse micellar solution.

Experimental

Yeast glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase (EC 1.1.1.49) grade II (suspension) (Boehringer

Mannheim) and glucose-6-phosphate and NADP⁺ (Sigma) were used. Bis(2-ethylhexyl)sodium sulphosuccinate (AOT) (American Cyanamid Company) was purified by the reported method⁵. The purified AOT was cut into small pieces and was dried over P₂O₅ in an evacuated desiccator for several hours prior to use. Polyoxyethylene(5)-octylphenol (Triton X-45) (Rohm & Haas) and n-heptane (hplc and spectroscopic grade, S. D. Fine Chemicals) were used.

Preparation of enzyme and substrate reverse micellar solutions : Concentrated stock solutions of enzymes, substrates etc. prepared in aqueous buffer at desired pH, were injected with microsyringes (Hamilton, U.S.A.) into the AOT-Triton X-45 (1 : 1)/n-heptane solution. The desired water content was set by an additional injection of the buffer solution into the reverse micellar solutions and the resulting mixture was shaken vigorously on a vortex mixer for a few tens of seconds until the formation of a homogeneous (optically transparent) solution^{6,7}. The buffer used to prepare the stock solutions of enzyme, coenzyme and substrate, was glycine-potassium hydroxide. pH was measured on an Elico LI-120 pH meter at 30°.

Activity measurement : Gilford response and Gilford 260 uv/vis spectrophotometers were used to measure the activity of the enzyme in reverse micellar solution. The temperature of the cell compartment was kept at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$ by circulating

water in the thermostat set of the spectrophotometer from an external thermostat which controlled temperature by a high precision electronic relay. The reverse micellar solutions containing substrate, coenzyme and desired amount of buffer, were incubated for a few minutes and the reaction was started by injecting 2–8 μ l of aqueous stock solution of enzyme to 1.0 ml of the incubation mixture. The initial velocity of enzyme reaction was measured by observing the increase in absorbance with time at the absorption maximum (340 nm) of NADPH. Adequate controls were run to ascertain that the increase in absorbance was not an artifact due to precipitation or separation of water in reverse micellar solution.

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